

INVESTMENT FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DEVELOPMENT OF GEO-ECOLOGICAL MONITORING OF THE RESTORATION OF LAND USED FOR TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE**Mamonov K.**

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Abstract

It has been established that the ongoing changes in the system of land relations necessitate a re-evaluation of approaches to ensuring their effective implementation. In the current context, land use is influenced by a range of factors, notably those reflecting the consequences of aggressive military operations. These lead to regional imbalances, a disruption of land and stakeholder relations, and the destruction of land and property assets. Issues concerning the development and application of modern monitoring technologies to enhance the efficiency of transport infrastructure land use are of particular relevance. In this context, the identification and consideration of environmental and investment factors are of particular importance.

As a result of the study, the objective of identifying investment factors for geo-ecological monitoring of transport infrastructure land use has been achieved.

The investment factors for geo-ecological monitoring of transport infrastructure land restoration have been identified, enabling the formation of a quantitative basis for the monitoring system and the development of a geoinformation framework for informed decision-making. It should be noted that the processes of identifying changes in the system of land restoration for transport infrastructure and creating an investment framework to attract investment resources and enhance the efficiency of land and property complex utilisation are of significant importance.

Keywords: investment factors, land reclamation, geo-ecological monitoring, transport infrastructure, geographic information systems, spatial planning, investment framework.

Introduction. The ongoing changes in the land relations system call for a rethinking of approaches to ensuring their effective implementation. In the current climate, land use is influenced by a range of factors, notably those reflecting the consequences of aggressive military operations. These lead to regional imbalances, disruptions in land and stakeholder relations, and the destruction of land and property assets. In this context, it should be noted that the utilisation of land for transport infrastructure is being hampered. Such infrastructure ensures the timely delivery of goods, the transport of passengers, and the efficient functioning of other sectors of the national economy.

To ensure the functioning of transport infrastructure, the following regulatory framework has been developed and is in force: Laws of Ukraine: the Law of Ukraine «On Transport», «On the Carriage of Dangerous Goods», «On the State Border of Ukraine», «On the Basic Principles of State Supervision (Control) in the

Sphere of Economic Activity», «On Technical Regulations and Conformity Assessment», «On Road Traffic», «On Freight Forwarding Activities», «On the Transit of Goods», «On Insurance», «On Ukraine's Accession to the Protocol to the Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road (CMR)», «On Ukraine's accession to the Agreement concerning the Adoption of Uniform Technical Prescriptions for Wheeled Vehicles, Equipment and Parts which can be Fitted and/or be Used on Wheeled Vehicles and the Conditions for Reciprocal Recognition of Official Approvals Granted on the Basis of these Prescriptions, 1958, as amended in 1995», «On Road Transport», «On urban electric transport» Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine «On the Approval of the Procedure and Rules for Compulsory Liability Insurance of Carriers of Dangerous Goods in the Event of Adverse Consequences During the Transport of Dangerous Goods», International Convention for the

Safety of Life at Sea, 1974, International Code for the Safety of Ships and Port Facilities, Directive 1999/63/EC of the Council of the European Union of 21 June 1999 «On the Agreement concerning the organisation of working time for seafarers, concluded between the European Community Shipowners» Association (ECSA) and the Federation of Transport Workers «Unions of the European Community (FTP)», Directive 1999/95/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of the European Union of 13 December 1999 «On the enforcement of provisions regarding seafarers» working hours on board ships calling at Community ports, Regulation (EC) No 725/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 March 2004 «On enhancing ship and port facility security», Directive 2005/65/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 October 2005 EC «On enhancing port security», the Merchant Shipping Code of Ukraine, Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine «On measures to enhance safety in maritime and river transport», «On the approval of the Regulations on crew member certificates», «Certain issues regarding the entry of foreign non-military vessels into river ports of Ukraine», Decree of the President of Ukraine № 262/2007 of 2 April 2007 «On Ukraine's accession to the Agreement on the International Carriage of Perishable Foodstuffs and on the Special Equipment to be Used for such Carriage (IBC)», etc.

Issues regarding the development and use of modern monitoring technologies to enhance the efficiency of transport infrastructure land use remain problematic. In particular, the identification and consideration of environmental and investment factors are of particular importance.

Thus, the research topic concerning the identification of investment factors influencing the development of geo-ecological monitoring of transport infrastructure land restoration is relevant, and its development is timely.

Justification of existing theoretical approaches.

In order to develop a geo-ecological monitoring system for the restoration of land used for transport infrastructure, its components and areas of implementation are identified [1–3]. Geo-ecological monitoring depends on the areas and specific applications of geographic information systems, which are determined by the following stages:

- the development of information and analytical support for the restoration of transport infrastructure land;
- the definition of spatial requirements;
- the formulation of factors and the construction of a multi-level system of indicators;
- the development and application of methods for assessing the level of transport infrastructure land restoration;
 - mathematical modelling of factors;
 - characterisation of geoinformation system tools;
 - the construction of attribute information;
 - the application of spatial support;
 - development of geoinformation monitoring maps;

- analysis and justification of changes occurring in the transport infrastructure land restoration system [4, 5].

The importance of identifying and applying investment factors is highlighted in the works [6, 7].

The processes of restoring land used for transport infrastructure are influenced by environmental factors, the formation and interaction of which are described in the following works [8, 9].

At the same time, issues relating to the development and application of geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure remain unresolved, taking into account the impact of investment factors.

The aim of the study is to identify the investment factors involved in the geo-ecological monitoring of land use for transport infrastructure.

Main section. The study identified the following investment indicators relating to the development and utilisation of geo-ecological monitoring for the restoration of transport infrastructure land:

- the level of support for investment activities in the transport infrastructure sector ($RTIL_{61}^1$);
- the fulfilment of contractual obligations in the field of foreign investment ($RTIL_{62}^1$);
- the effectiveness of stakeholder relations in the field of transport infrastructure investment ($RTIL_{63}^1$);
- the creation of conditions for the preservation, development and utilisation of domestic scientific, technical and innovative potential ($RTIL_{64}^1$);
- the effective use of market mechanisms to promote innovative activity and support entrepreneurship in the scientific and industrial sectors ($RTIL_{65}^1$);
- implementation of measures to support international scientific and technological cooperation, technology transfer, protection of domestic products in the domestic market and their promotion in foreign markets ($RTIL_{66}^1$);
- training of personnel in the field of innovation ($RTIL_{67}^1$);
- training of personnel in the field of investment ($RTIL_{68}^1$);
- the development and implementation of innovative projects ($RTIL_{69}^1$);
- the establishment and use of compensation for damage to and destruction of certain categories of immovable property resulting from hostilities, terrorist acts and sabotage caused by the armed aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, and the State Register of Property Damaged and Destroyed as a Result of Hostilities, terrorist acts and sabotage caused by the armed aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine ($RTIL_{610}^1$);
- the use of funds for the restoration of destroyed property and railway transport infrastructure: main public railway lines and the technical structures located on them, transmission equipment directly used to ensure the transport process, in particular railway stations, passenger station complexes, public-use tracks, traction substations, catenary systems and other technical power supply installations, signalling, centralisation, interlocking and train control systems ($RTIL_{611}^1$);

- road transport: public roads; streets and roads in towns and other settlements; road transport production facilities (excluding rolling stock) (*RTIL*₆₁₂¹);
- air transport: aerodromes and aerodrome facilities (*RTIL*₆₁₃¹);
- maritime transport: port infrastructure facilities (excluding movable property) (*RTIL*₆₁₄¹);
- inland waterway transport (excluding movable property) (*RTIL*₆₁₅¹);
- the compilation and completeness of information on damaged and destroyed immovable property entered in the State Register of Property Damaged and Destroyed as a Result of Hostilities, Terrorist Acts and Sabotage Caused by the Armed Aggression of the Russian Federation, in accordance with the Procedure for submitting information reports on damaged and destroyed immovable property as a result of hostilities, terrorist acts and sabotage caused by the military aggression of the Russian Federation, approved by Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine № 380 of 26 March 2022 «On the collection, processing and recording of information regarding immovable property damaged or destroyed as a result of hostilities, terrorist acts and sabotage caused by the military aggression of the Russian Federation» (*RTIL*₆₁₆¹);
- ensuring stakeholder relations in the field of transport infrastructure reconstruction (*RTIL*₆₁₇¹);
- the effective application of the Unified Digital System for the Restoration of Ukraine (DREAM) as an integrated information and communication system designed to automate the management of restoration projects, as well as to monitor the implementation of these projects and the use of financial resources (*RTIL*₆₁₈¹);
- the comprehensive restoration of transport infrastructure (*RTIL*₆₁₉¹);
- ensuring that the central executive authority responsible for formulating and implementing state policy on the reconstruction of regions, territories and infrastructure affected by the Russian Federation's armed aggression against Ukraine is prompted to submit a proposal to the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine regarding the recognition of a settlement as destroyed or significantly damaged, recognition of a destroyed or significantly damaged settlement as one subject to priority restoration at the expense of the state budget shall be carried out by the village, settlement or city council or the military (military-civilian) administration of the settlement (if established) (*RTIL*₆₂₀¹);
- the development and implementation of restoration projects concerning restoration sites located in the temporarily occupied territory of Ukraine, as defined in accordance with the Law of Ukraine «On Ensuring the Rights and Freedoms of Citizens and the Legal Regime in the Temporarily Occupied Territory of Ukraine», to be carried out following de-occupation and the cessation of active hostilities in the relevant territory (*RTIL*₆₂₁¹);
- financing of restoration projects, carried out using funds from the state budget (including the State Fund for Regional Development, the Fund for the Restoration of Property and Destroyed Infrastructure, and the Fund for the Elimination of the Consequences of Armed Aggression) and local budgets (*RTIL*₆₂₂¹);

- funds from international financial organisations, other creditors and investors (*RTIL*₆₂₃¹);
- the index of changes in capital investment at regional level (*RTIL*₆₂₄¹);
- the index of changes in the number of enterprises in the transport infrastructure sector (*RTIL*₆₂₅¹);
- the index of changes in personnel costs of business entities in the transport infrastructure sector (*RTIL*₆₂₆¹);
- levels of compensation or partial compensation for the cost of engineering and transport infrastructure facilities constructed by the applicant or an investor with significant investments, which are necessary for the implementation of the investment project (*RTIL*₆₂₇¹);
- electronic information exchange between the register and other automated systems, electronic information resources and state registers (*RTIL*₆₂₈¹).

Conclusions. Thus, the investment factors for the geo-ecological monitoring of land restoration in transport infrastructure have been identified, enabling the establishment of a quantitative basis for the monitoring system and the development of a geo-information framework to support informed decision-making. It should be noted that the processes of identifying changes in the system of transport infrastructure land restoration and creating an investment framework for attracting investment resources and improving the efficiency of land and property complex utilisation are of significant importance.

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